

MoveD – ORD Guidelines for Swiss Movement Laboratories

Section 3: Data Processing

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1. Metadata

The following metadata should be collected during data processing. If pre-processing steps have been performed during data collection, please include this information in as much detail as possible.

Table 1: Metadata collected during data processing.

Title	Content/Format	Comment
General Information		
Date of data processing	[YYYY-MM-DD]	According to International Organization for Standardization 8601
Software(s) used for data processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Name Manufacturer Version Type of data that were processed 	Please describe the type of data which were collected in the following form: sensor type and outcome of primary interest Examples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marker-based kinematics Sensor-based kinematics Video-based (markerless) kinematics Surface EMG Force plate kinetics Spatiotemporal parameters EEG Medical imaging Plantar pressure 2D video
Sampling rate	[Hz]	If re-sampled after collection, otherwise state that the sampling rate has not been changed
Quality check (if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe how data quality was assessed e.g. visually by the four-eye-principle Automatic outlier detection and removal ... 	For a manual, visual quality check please indicate the criteria used For automatic outlier detection, describe the calculation method/algorithm used For IMU's refer to recommendations for quality assessment of the ISB (Cereatti et al., 2024)

Processing of EMG (if applicable)		
Filter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type of filter (Butterworth, Chebyshev, etc.) Low/high pass cut-off frequencies [Hz] Slopes of the cut-offs (if applicable) 	According to standards for reporting EMG data https://isek.org/emg-standards/ (Merletti, 1999). Further information on https://cede.isek.org/
Rectification	Yes/No (full or half-wave)	
EMG amplitude processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No processing RMS ARV MAV IEMG 	RMS = root mean square ARV = average rectified value MAV = mean absolute value IEMG = integrated EMG (area under the curve)
Normalization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MVC for EMG (including how subjects were trained, etc.) RVC Amplitude normalization (to mean value or peak value) Time normalization No normalization 	According to standards for reporting EMG data https://isek.org/emg-standards/ (Merletti, 1999). Further information on https://cede.isek.org/ .
Exclusion of trials/muscles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Criteria for exclusion of trials/muscles -> e.g. artefacts (how are they defined as artefacts), missing signal What part of the data is deleted (raw data, processed data) 	
Analyzed outcomes	Each mean, maximal or minimal value over trial (please report which variable you used and during which phase of the movement it was extracted): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> RMS of amplitude ARV of amplitude Rectified full wave EMG signal Envelope On/off detection e.g. on/off time Area under the curve slope 	RMS = root mean square ARV = average rectified value Also include a reference to the chosen calculation methods for EMG outcomes in the metadata.

Processing of EEG data (if applicable)		
Filter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type of filter (basic FIR filter, FFT linear filter, short infinite impulse response, notch filtering, etc.) Low/high pass cut-off frequency 	
Re-referencing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specify reference electrode State if data was re-referenced to a specific electrode or if average reference was computed 	
Resampling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specify if and how you re-sampled data 	
Artifact removal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specify which channels were rejected and whether automatically or manually (if applicable) Specify if an individual component analysis was performed and which algorithm was used 	
Data epoch extraction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> List which event type and epoch limit was used to extract data epochs Baseline removal latency range [ms] 	
Head model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which head model was used 	
Export (if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> File type after export 	
Exclusion of trials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Criteria for exclusion of data trials/single joints What part of the data is deleted (raw data, processed data)? 	

Processing of marker data (if applicable)		
Labelling	Marker names including anatomical reference point	If the labelling is identical to what is reported in the metadata of collect, please refer to the corresponding document and do not duplicate it.
Pipelines	Name of the pipelines that were used including chosen settings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject calibration: describe the used calibration method • Gap filling: name (e.g. Rigid Body, Woltring) and max. gap length) • Filter: name, cut-off frequency, order, type • Data processing: if e.g. Plug-in-Gait is used, describe the pipeline and properties 	Describe all the relevant pre-processing steps that are needed to reproduce data processing
Events (if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Criteria for placement of events, e.g. automatic detection (force threshold/used markers) or manual setting (used markers) 	
Calculation method	Reference to the calculation method for kinematics, kinetics (if applicable)	Examples of calculation methods are Newton-Euler, Lagrange and Inverse Dynamics or Forward Dynamics Indicate in which direction positive values are.
Naming convention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name of the files for export and their meaning • List of abbreviations 	If data is exported. Please describe the abbreviations used in the dataset e.g. LF = lateral flexion.
Export (if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • File type after export 	
Exclusion of trials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Criteria for exclusion of data trials/single joints • What part of the data is deleted (raw data, processed data)? 	
Normalization	Time normalization yes/no For spatiotemporal parameters leg length normalization yes/no	If yes, define criteria
Analyzed outcomes angles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mean value + SD • Maximal value • Range (min & max) • ... 	Include a reference to the chosen calculation methods for kinematic outcomes in the metadata. If only mean values are reported, please state from what number of individual trials the mean was calculated.

Analyzed spatiotemporal outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mean value + SD • Absolute value (e.g. for step time) or percentage (e.g. for foot off) 	<p>Include a reference to the chosen calculation methods in the metadata.</p> <p>If only mean values are reported, please state from what number of individual trials the mean was calculated</p>
<i>Processing of kinetics (if applicable)</i>		
Naming convention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name of the files for export and their meaning • List of abbreviations 	<p>Please describe the abbreviations used in the dataset e.g. LF = lateral flexion.</p>
Pipelines	<p>Name of the pipelines used, including the chosen settings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Filtering: name of filter, cut-off frequency, order, type • Model used to calculate moments (e.g. Plug-in Gait, BodyBuilder, ...) 	<p>Describe if filtered force/ marker data are used for model calculation</p>
Export (if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • File type after export 	
Exclusion of trials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Criteria for exclusion of forces/moments • What part of the data is deleted (raw data, processed data) 	
Normalization	<p>Is kinetic data normalized to body weight (e.g. % bodyweight or kg^{-1}) yes/no</p>	<p>Also describe if other normalization methods were used</p>
Analyzed outcomes moments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mean value + SD • Maximal value • Range (min & max) • etc. 	<p>Include a reference to the chosen calculation methods in the metadata. Refer to Derrick et al. (2020) for help.</p> <p>If only mean values are reported, please state from what number of individual trials the mean was calculated</p>
Analyzed outcomes forces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mean value + SD • Maximal value • Range (min & max) • ... 	<p>Include a reference to the chosen calculation methods in the metadata. Refer to Derrick et al. (2020) for help.</p> <p>If only mean values are reported, please state from what number of individual trials the mean was calculated</p>

Processing of IMU data (if applicable)		
Naming convention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Name of the files for export and their meaning List of abbreviations 	Please describe the abbreviations used in the dataset e.g. LF = lateral flexion including in which direction positive values are.
Filter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Name of filter Cut-off frequency Order Type 	
Export (if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> File type after export 	
Normalization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time or other normalization procedure – please specify 	
Kinematic model used	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Name of the model including reference Include parameterization (generalized coordinates, transformation equations, calculation method) 	For more information and templates refer to the ISB recommendations on wearable inertial measurement technology (Cereatti et al., 2024).
Coordinate system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Include the definition of the anatomical and joint coordination system 	For more information refer to the ISB recommendations on wearable inertial measurement technology (Cereatti et al., 2024).
Sensor fusion algorithm (if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Include a reference to the sensor fusion algorithm you have used 	For more information refer to the ISB recommendations on wearable inertial measurement technology (Cereatti et al., 2024).
Analyzed outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Angles Velocity/acceleration Magnetometer Gyroscope 	
Exclusion of trials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Criteria for exclusion of forces/moments What part of the data is deleted (raw data, processed data)? 	

<i>Processing of plantar pressure (if applicable)</i>		
Processing steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Masking • Definition of the region of interest and the analyzed segments 	Please add the information that is relevant to your measurement device and methods chosen.
Exclusion of trials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Criteria for exclusion of trials 	
Analyzed outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peak pressure • Mean pressure • Location of peak pressure 	If only mean values are reported, please state from what number of individual trials the mean was calculated
<i>Processing of imaging data (if applicable)</i>		
Algorithms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applied algorithms for image processing 	
Exclusion of trials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Criteria for exclusion of images 	
Analyzed outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How was the grading performed? • Which parameters were calculated and which approach was used (e.g. ossification ratio in ultrasound)? • etc. 	
<i>Processing of 2D video data (if applicable)</i>		
Calculation method for joint angles (if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If segment lines were drawn to calculate joint angles, please specify which reference points were used 	

Data and report management standards for different measurement systems are also available from the clinical movement analysis society of UK and Ireland on <https://cmasuki.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/CMAS-Standards-2024-v18.pdf> (Stewart et al., 2023).

2. Source code

2.1 Minimal requirement:

- Codes are saved with version control
- A regular back-up of the code is performed
- Codes are reviewed (internally) before being used
- Code is organized in folders
- A readme file is included
- The readme file should contain the information needed to replicate the analysis (this includes the analysis environment; package versions)
- A clear link to the data location/repository should be provided, as well as a clear explanation of how to import the data

2.2 Ideal case:

- Code is uploaded to an openly accessible repository e.g. GitHub.
- At the very least, the commit for the version used in the analysis should be mentioned. Ideally, the used version is referenced as a release with a DOI/URI (using for example Zenodo to generate a DOI for the release).
- Code does not contain references to local folders so as to ensure interoperability
- All code is properly explained through inline comments so that others can use it without further instructions
- In the ideal case, code can be published in such a way that the data is directly downloaded from the repository and read when the code is run.

3. Description of source codes/readme file

3.1 Minimal requirement:

- Project title
- Build status (development, testing, usage)
- Purpose of code/short description of project that the code was used for
- Code style
- Date/time period when code was written
- Contributors to the code
- Copyright of the code/applicable licence <https://choosealicense.com/> for help
- Features of the code or the different parts of the code
- How the code should be used

3.2 Ideal case:

- Detailed high-level documentation: Description of different code components and how they are linked. The aim is to get an overview of the code and know where to start looking if a specific problem is encountered.

4. Open file format

In this section we present recommendations as to which open data formats the files (exported from the measurement system) should be converted to. It is, however, more important to adhere to the “linked open data” framework as described in <https://handbook.opendata.swiss/de/content/glossar/bibliothek/linked-open-data.html>

You may be able to export your data in another file format which is not listed in the following table. Please ensure that you adhere to the “linked open data” framework mentioned above. Moreover, if additional information is generated by the measurement system, such as patient reports in the form of a PDF, for example, please add this information as well, since PDF is an open file format.

Table 2: Recommendations for open data formats for movement data.

File extension (closed file format, exported from the measurement system)	File extension (open file format, to be converted from the closed file format)	Comment
Marker-based motion capture & force data		
C3d	C3d	C3d files can be opened/handled using open-source tools https://pypi.org/project/pyc3dserver/
Enf	txt	
Mat	Json	
EMG data		
Mat	Json	
C3d	C3d	
Csv	csv	
Txt	txt	
IMU data		
C3d	C3d	C3d files can be opened/handled using open-source tools https://pypi.org/project/pyc3dserver/
Mat	Json	
Csv	Csv	
Mvnx	Json	
Xlsx	Csv	
fbx	C3d	
bvh	C3d	

2D Video data		
Mov	Mpeg4 or avi	Conversion of video formats to open-source formats (can be done using open-source tools, e.g. FFmpeg)
Mp4		
Flv		
Avi		
Avchd		
Wmv		
mkv		
...		
Plantar pressure		
Csv, xml, or proprietary data types	Csv or xml	Xml possible for raw pressure data in Zebris
EEG		
Edf	Edf, vhdr, vmrk, eeg, or csv	Each measurement system is different, use what applies to your system
Vhdr		
Vmrk		
Eeg		
Set		
Fdt		
Bdf		
Imaging data (Ultrasound, CT, MRI)		
Jpg, mp4, avi	Jpg, mpeg4, avi	
DICOM	DICOM, DCM, DCM30	

5. References

- Cereatti, A., Gurchiek, R., Mündermann, A., Fantozzi, S., Horak, F., Delp, S., & Aminian, K. (2024). ISB recommendations on the definition, estimation, and reporting of joint kinematics in human motion analysis applications using wearable inertial measurement technology. *Journal of Biomechanics*, *173*, 112225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2024.112225>
- Derrick, T. R., Van Den Bogert, A. J., Cereatti, A., Dumas, R., Fantozzi, S., & Leardini, A. (2020). ISB recommendations on the reporting of intersegmental forces and moments during human motion analysis. *Journal of Biomechanics*, *99*, 109533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2019.109533>
- International Organization for Standardization. (2024). *Date and time format*. <https://www.iso.org/iso-8601-date-and-time-format.html>
- Merletti, R. (1999). Standards for Reporting EMG data. *Journal of Electromyography and Kinesiology*, *9*(1):III-IV.
- Stewart, C., Eve, L., Durham, S., Holmes, G., Stebbins, J., Harrington, M., Corbett, M., Kiernan, D., Kidgell, V., Jarvis, S., Daly, C., & Noble, J. (2023). Clinical Movement Analysis Society – UK and Ireland: Clinical Movement Analysis Standards. *Gait & Posture*, *106*, 86–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2023.08.006>